

VARIABILITY STUDIES IN SELECTED GENOTYPES OF JAMUN (*Syzygium cumini*)Swaroop B. Rodge¹, G. G. Jadhav², U. A. Raut³, Pranjali G. Laharia¹, S. P. Mahalle¹, L. R. Raut¹¹PG Student, Department of Fruit Science, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, (MS) India²Deputy Director of Horticulture, Central Research Station, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola (MS) India³Associate Professor, Department of Fruit Science, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola (MS) India

swarooprodge123@gmail.com

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Abstract

A study was conducted on a thirty-year-old jamun orchard at the Experimental Farm, Central Research Station, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, during the years 2023 and 2024 to study the extent of variability in leaf, flower, fruit and seed characters of different genotypes of jamun. The twenty-two selected genotypes revealed wide variability with respect to leaf, flower, fruit and seed characteristics, including the leaf area (36.95 to 66.07 cm²), number of flowers per panicle (32.42 to 64.20), number of fruits per panicle (19.05 to 34.90), number of fruits per cluster (6.72 to 11.10), fruit weight (6.12 to 16.30 g), fruit length (17.60 to 36.20 mm), fruit width (16.40 to 27.70 mm), fruit volume (2.60 to 12.50 cm³), pulp weight (4.05 to 11.70 g), pulp percentage (60.68 to 82.80%), seed weight (1.50 to 4.60 g), seed percentage (16.66 to 39.30%), pulp-to-seed ratio (4.90), and yield per tree (35.50 to 71.20 kg/tree). Fruit biochemical characters such as, TSS (12.80 to 19.37 °B), acidity (0.26 to 0.50%), total sugars (4.48 to 14.68%), reducing sugars (5.52 to 10.06%), non-reducing sugars (2.56 to 6.03%), anthocyanin (134.60 to 160.20 mg/100 g), and antioxidant activity (81.95 to 95.57%). Based on yield, yield-contributing traits, and biochemical characteristics, the genotypes AKLJ-14 and AKLJ-5 were identified as promising for future jamun breeding and improvement programs.

Key words: Jamun, *Syzygium cumini*, variability, genotype

Introduction:

The Jamun (*Syzygium cumini* L. Skeels), often referred to as the Indian blackberry, Jambu, Java plum, Black plum, Jambul or Portuguese plum in English, (Sharma, *et al.* 2012) is a tiny fruit tree that grows wild in India and is a member of the Myrtaceae family. Its chromosome number is 2n = 40 Singh (1969). India, or the East Indies, is where jamun originated. Jamun is one of the most perishable small fruit crops. It is utilized in traditional medicine and has a higher nutritional and therapeutic value than other minor fruit crops. Because of its many chemical and therapeutic qualities, jamun fruit has a promising restorative effect. Apart from being a source of various minerals, sugars, and pharmacokinetics, it is also a good source of iron and pectin (Singh, *et al.* 1967). Anthocyanins, phenols, and protein are abundant in jamun fruit. The fruit juice and seed include the glycoside jambolin and the alkaloid jambosin, which inhibit or prevent the diastatic conversion of starch to sugars. Fruit pulp contains 83.7–85.8 gm of moisture, 14 gm of carbohydrates, 0.32–0.4 gm of ash, 8.3–15 mg of calcium, 35 mg of magnesium, 15.–16.2 mg of phosphorus, 1.2–1.62 mg of iron, 55 mg of potassium, 0.23 mg of copper, 13 mg of sulphur, 80 I.U. of vitamin A, 5.7–18 mg of ascorbic acid, and 7 mg of choline in every 100 g (Nath, *et al.* 2008).

Due to factors like climate change, widespread urbanization, development projects, lack of commercialization, and a lack of awareness about the significance of these resources, jamun's genetic resources are seriously threatened with extinction. Advancement and restoration of genetic diversity are crucial for preserving the current diversity of jamun and achieving a sustainable future based on the utilization of genetic resources. The ultimate goal of using diverse breeding techniques to produce genetically improved commercially grown jamun with high yield and other quality characteristics calls for a multifaceted strategy that includes preserving and conserving the rich germplasm as well as identifying superior genotypes. Variations can be effectively used to increase a species adaptation, such as drought tolerance or the selection of a genotype that is best for growth or fruit quality, among other things. Any fruit crop development program's success mostly rests on the selection of superior genotypes, which is heavily reliant on the genetic variety present in the population. Increased diversity increases the likelihood that superior and desired genotypes will develop.

Material and methodology:

The present study was carried out in 2023–2024 at the Experimental Farm, Central Research Station, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, on a thirty year's old jamun orchard. Akola is situated at 307–457 meter altitude from sea level of 20.42° N latitude and 72.02° E longitude and has marginal tropical climate. In the present

investigation out of fifty-five genotypes promising twenty-two genotypes were selected.

One plant from each treatment (i.e., genotype) was selected, marked, and kept under observation. For recording various data, ten shoots in each direction were tagged. Observations were recorded following the methods described by Kaulgud *et al.* (1997), Rodriguez-Medina *et al.* (2010), and Patil (2014). Since the study is based on single-plant observations, samples were collected from each direction (East, West, North, and South), with each direction considered as one replication. The observed characteristics were then subjected to RBD (Randomized Block Design) analysis. The fruits were analyzed for both physical and bio-chemical parameters.

Result & Discussion:

For physical parameters:

Significant variation was observed among genotypes regarding leaf area (Table 1). The highest leaf area was recorded in genotype AKLJ-14 (66.07 cm²), whereas lowest in AKLJ-13 (36.95 cm²). The mean value of leaf area was found to be (49.92 cm²). Number of flowers per panicle was recorded highest in AKLJ-14 (64.20) and lowest in AKLJ-12 (32.42). Similar results were observed by Anushma *et al.* (2018). Genotype AKLJ-14 recorded highest number of fruits per panicle (34.90) and lowest was recorded in genotype AKLJ-4 (19.05). Similar results were observed by Kumar *et al.* (2022). The highest fruit weight was found in AKLJ-5 (16.30 g), and lowest fruit weight in AKLJ-4 (6.12g), with average mean of (9.36 g). Maximum fruit length was recorded in the genotype AKLJ-5 (36.20 mm) and minimum in AKLJ-4 (17.60 mm) also maximum fruit width was observed in AKLJ-5 (27.70 mm) and minimum in AKLJ-4 (16.40 mm). Genotype AKLJ-5 recorded highest fruit volume (12.50 cm³) and lowest fruit volume found in genotype AKLJ-4 (2.60 cm³), with average mean value of (6.70 cm³). The maximum number of fruits per cluster was found in AKLJ-14 (11.10) and minimum was found in AKLJ-5 (6.72), with average mean value (8.25). Similarly highest number of fruits per 100g was observed in genotype AKLJ-4 (16.30) and lowest in genotype AKLJ-5 (6.07). Pulp weight was recorded highest in genotype AKLJ-5 (11.70 g) and lowest in genotype AKLJ-13 (4.05 g). The mean value of pulp weight was found to be (6.90 g). Genotype AKLJ-18 recorded highest pulp per cent (82.80%) and lowest pulp per cent in genotype AKLJ-13 (60.68%) with average mean of 73.21 per cent. The maximum seed weight was found in AKLJ-5 (4.60 g) and minimum in AKLJ-4 (1.50 g) with average mean value of (2.42 g). Genotype AKLJ-18 recorded highest pulp: seed ratio (4.90%) and lowest in genotype AKLJ-13 (1.56%). The maximum yield per tree was recorded in genotype AKLJ-14 (71.20 kg) and lowest in genotype AKLJ-4 (35.50 kg). The average mean value of yield per tree was found to be (50.45 kg).

For Biochemical parameters

Significant variation was observed among genotypes regarding TSS (Table 2). The highest TSS was recorded in genotype AKLJ-14 (19.37⁰Brix), while the lowest TSS was found in AKLJ-17 (12.80⁰Brix) with mean value of (16.48⁰Brix). Genotype AKLJ-17 exhibited the highest acidity (0.50%), whereas AKLJ-14 had the lowest acidity (0.26%). These results are consistent with those reported by Singh *et al.* (2012). AKLJ-14 also had the highest anthocyanin content (160.20 mg/100g), while AKLJ-4 had the lowest (134.60 mg/100g), with mean value of (145.10 mg/100g). Similar results were observed by Alam *et al.* (2020). The highest antioxidant activity was found in AKLJ-14 (95.57%) whereas AKLJ-4 had the lowest (81.95%). The highest total sugars was found in AKLJ-11 (14.68%), and the lowest in AKLJ-17 (8.48%). The mean value of total sugars was (11.49%). For reducing sugars, AKLJ-14 had the highest content (10.06%), while AKLJ-7 had the lowest (5.25%). Non-reducing sugars among the jamun genotypes ranged from 2.56% to 6.03%, with AKLJ-11 recording the highest (6.03%) and AKLJ-17 the lowest (2.56%).

Conclusion:

It was observed that genotype AKLJ-14 had the highest number of flowers per panicle, number of fruits per panicle, number of fruits per cluster, yield per tree, as well as the highest TSS, reducing sugars, anthocyanin content, and antioxidant activity. Genotype AKLJ-5 exhibited the maximum fruit weight, fruit length, fruit breadth, fruit volume, pulp weight, seed weight, pulp percentage, and pulp-to-seed ratio. Genotype AKLJ-11 had the highest total sugars and non-reducing sugars. Based on overall performance and yield and yield-contributing characteristics, the genotypes AKLJ-14, AKLJ-5, and AKLJ-3 were identified as promising for future improvement programs.

Fig 1. Variability in fruits of Jamun genotypes

Reference:

1. Agrawal, V., Rangare, N. R., & Nair, R. (2017). Variability studies in different accessions of Jamun (*Syzygium cumini* skeels) from Madhya Pradesh. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 5(3), 07-11.
2. Alam, M., Mani, A., Mitra, S., & Bauri, F. K. (2020). Flowering, fruiting and physio-chemical properties of jamun (*Syzygium cumini* Skeels) grown in Nadia district of West Bengal. *Advances in BioResearch*, 11(5), 1-5.
3. Anushma, P. L. and Anuradha Sane. 2018. Assessing variability in morphological traits of Jamun (*Syzygium cumini* Skeels) genotypes. *Journal of Plant Development Sciences*, 10 (11): 629-632.
4. Devi P S, Thangam M. Desai A R. and Adsule P G. 2002. Studies on variability in physico-chemical

characters of different jamun (*Syzygium cumini*) accessions from Goa. *Indian Journal of Horticulture* 59:153-156.

5. Ekta, P. Ningot, Megha H. Dahale, S. G. Bharad and Nagre, P. K. 2017. Studies on variability in physico-chemical characteristics of Jamun (*Syzygium cumini* Skeels) genotypes from eastern Maharashtra. *Life Science International Research Journal*, 4 (1):215-217.
6. Kaulgud, S. N., Supe, V. S., Karale, A. R. and Keskar, B. G. 1997. Descriptor of Pomegranate. Department of Horticulture, MPKV Rahuri.
7. Mahalle, S. P., Jadhav, G. G., Raut, U. A., Khairkar, N. A., Deshmukh, K. Y., Deshmukh, R. N., and Tadas, V. S. 2023. Diversity in morphological characters of Khirni (*Manilkara hexandra*). *Madras agricultural journal*, 110(10-12): 108-11.
8. Naitam, P. C. 2018. Physico-chemical evaluation of Jamun fruits of different genotypes, M.sc (Agri.) Thesis, submitted to Department of Horticulture, Dr. P.D.K.V, Akola, M.H., (India).
9. Nath V, Kumar D. and Pandey V. 2008. *Fruits for the future: Well versed Arid and Semi-Arid Fruits*. Satish Serial Publishing House, 403, Express Tower, Commercial Complex, Azadpur, Delhi. p264.
10. Patel, S. K., Halder, A., & Deb, P. (2023). Studies on Some Physical and Chemical Characters on Diversity of Some Local Jamun (*Syzygium cumini* Skeels) Genotypes. *International Journal of Plant & Soil Science*, 35(14), 109-114.
11. Patil, R. 2014. Genetic variability and divergence studies in Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) Ph.D. Thesis submitted to Dr. PDKV, Akola, M.S. India.
12. Prabhuraj, S., Swamy, G. S. K., Athani, S. I., Patil, B. R., Hulamani, N. C. and Patil, P. B. 2002a. Variability in morphological characteristics of Jamun (*Syzygium cumini* Skeels) trees. *My Forest*, 38(2): 187-190
13. Raut, U. A., Jadhav, S. B., and Mahalle, S. P., 2022. Character association studies in tamarind (*Tamarindus indica* L.) for yield and yield contributing character. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 11(11): 973-982
14. Rodríguez-Medina, N. N., Fermin, G. A., Ealdes-infante, J., Velasquez, B., D., Martinez, F., Rodriguez, J. and Rhode, W. 2010. Illustrated descriptor for guava (*Psidium guajava* L.). *Acta Hort.* 849:103-109.
15. Sharma S, Mehta B K. Mehta D. Nagar H. and Mishra A. 2012. A review on pharmacological activity of *Syzygium cumini* extracts using different solvent and their effective doses. *International Research Journal of Pharmacology* 3:54-58.
16. Santosh Kumar, Md. Feza Ahmad, Sanjay Sahay, Muneshwar Prasad and Samik Sengupta 2022. Studies on variability of morphological features of different genotypes of Jamun (*Syzygium cumini* Skeels). *The Pharma Innovation Journal* 2022; 11(2): 976-979.
17. Singh, S., Krishnamurthy, S., and Katyal, S. L. 1967. *Fruit culture in India*, ICAR, New Delhi. 9:255.
18. Singh R.1969. *Fruits*. National book trust, New Delhi. 213p.
19. Talang, H. D., Rekha, A., Dinesh, M. R., & Shivashankar, K. S. (2017). Physico-chemical variability of selected genotypes of jamun (*Syzygium cumini* Skeels). *Indian Horticulture Journal*, 7(1), 64-66.

Table 1. Variation in leaf, flower, fruit and seed characters of different genotypes of jamun

Genotype	Leaf area (cm ²)	No. of flowers per panicle	No. of fruits per panicle	Fruit weight (g)	Fruit length (mm)	Fruit width (mm)	Fruit volume (cm ³)	No. of fruits per cluster	No. of fruits per 100 g	Pulp weight (g)	Pulp percentage (%)	Seed weight (g)	Seed percentage (%)	Pulp: seed ratio (%)	Yield per tree (kg)
AKLJ-1	43.20	42.20	31.90	9.60	27.20	25.40	8.10	6.92	10.40	6.80	70.82	2.80	29.16	2.42	47.30
AKLJ-2	51.25	33.32	24.12	11.15	30.00	24.40	8.50	8.55	8.92	8.25	74.03	2.90	26.00	2.85	35.50
AKLJ-3	48.35	35.40	25.92	12.70	28.00	27.20	8.70	7.42	7.85	9.80	77.12	2.90	22.84	3.39	61.70
AKLJ-4	40.40	52.00	19.05	6.12	17.60	16.40	2.60	7.75	16.30	4.52	74.92	1.50	24.73	3.13	35.50
AKLJ-5	62.47	51.00	32.97	16.30	36.20	27.70	12.50	6.72	6.07	11.70	71.77	4.60	28.20	2.55	65.30
AKLJ-6	55.25	46.47	27.17	6.60	23.80	21.00	3.40	8.02	15.12	4.20	63.56	2.40	36.43	1.76	51.20
AKLJ-7	50.00	43.97	26.87	7.60	25.60	20.40	5.50	7.65	13.12	5.60	73.64	2.00	26.34	2.81	40.00
AKLJ-8	38.37	36.52	24.75	7.17	26.20	21.05	5.70	8.65	13.92	5.17	72.30	1.97	27.53	2.65	42.40
AKLJ-9	47.12	42.70	28.05	6.50	24.30	20.20	6.10	6.92	15.35	4.10	62.82	2.40	37.17	1.76	46.60
AKLJ-10	55.02	46.80	31.87	8.42	26.80	23.30	5.90	8.50	11.85	5.95	70.88	2.40	28.56	2.49	52.10
AKLJ-11	61.97	37.15	27.30	6.67	23.90	20.40	3.30	8.15	14.95	4.62	69.60	2.00	30.11	2.38	50.30
AKLJ-12	45.25	32.42	26.90	9.97	32.40	22.30	7.80	9.37	10.02	7.60	76.39	2.32	23.33	3.27	45.50
AKLJ-13	36.95	43.57	30.07	6.65	23.50	20.60	3.50	7.02	15.02	4.05	60.68	2.60	39.30	1.56	38.40
AKLJ-14	66.07	64.20	34.90	10.42	30.00	25.00	8.20	11.10	9.60	8.42	81.00	1.92	18.71	4.35	71.20
AKLJ-15	57.85	58.37	31.85	8.55	28.00	21.60	6.10	7.37	11.65	6.40	75.09	2.10	24.59	3.06	60.20
AKLJ-16	42.95	38.82	26.97	9.27	30.00	22.20	6.70	8.88	10.75	6.95	75.25	2.27	24.61	3.07	56.60
AKLJ-17	41.22	41.22	22.97	12.12	29.30	23.60	7.90	9.20	8.20	9.52	78.55	2.60	21.43	3.67	51.20
AKLJ-18	53.05	47.27	33.75	9.50	27.60	22.50	6.60	8.20	10.52	7.82	82.80	1.60	16.88	4.90	47.50
AKLJ-19	48.40	47.80	28.75	9.22	27.00	23.00	6.70	7.95	10.85	6.85	74.27	2.30	25.04	2.97	53.10
AKLJ-20	46.00	35.52	25.90	9.97	28.70	23.50	6.90	9.77	10.02	7.52	75.49	2.37	24.08	3.14	55.40
AKLJ-21	51.27	41.22	29.05	9.40	28.10	23.20	7.80	7.02	10.60	6.90	74.01	2.40	25.67	2.88	48.80
AKLJ-22	55.90	52.70	29.22	12.12	31.60	26.60	8.90	10.55	8.20	9.12	75.74	2.90	24.10	3.13	54.30
Range	36.95-66.07	32.42-64.20	19.05-34.90	6.12-16.30	17.60-36.20	16.40-27.70	2.60-12.50	6.72-11.10	6.07-16.30	4.05-11.70	60.68-82.80	1.50-4.60	16.88-39.30	1.56-4.90	35.50-71.20
Mean	49.92	44.12	28.19	9.36	27.53	22.79	6.70	8.25	11.33	6.90	73.21	2.42	26.58	2.91	50.45
SE(m)±	0.22	0.55	0.19	0.22	0.31	0.23	0.13	0.12	0.31	0.22	1.44	0.10	1.43	0.16	0.10
C.D at 5%	0.64	1.56	0.54	0.63	0.89	0.66	0.37	0.34	0.89	0.64	4.09	0.28	4.05	0.47	0.30

Table 2. Variation in biochemical characters of different genotypes of jamun

Genotype	TSS (^o Brix)	Acidity (%)	Total sugars (%)	Reducing sugars (%)	Non-reducing sugars (%)	Anthocyanin (mg/100g)	Antioxidant activity (%)
AKLJ-1	17.70	0.33	12.30	8.34	3.95	139.30	87.12
AKLJ-2	15.20	0.41	10.18	7.53	2.65	137.40	91.02
AKLJ-3	16.30	0.37	11.67	7.79	3.88	147.30	92.30
AKLJ-4	14.40	0.47	9.78	6.63	3.15	134.60	81.95
AKLJ-5	15.60	0.45	11.13	7.33	3.80	142.10	95.20
AKLJ-6	14.10	0.48	9.26	5.65	3.61	140.70	90.00
AKLJ-7	14.60	0.43	9.78	5.25	4.52	138.32	88.87
AKLJ-8	19.30	0.30	14.17	9.72	4.44	141.30	90.15
AKLJ-9	14.60	0.46	10.48	7.22	3.26	135.70	87.07
AKLJ-10	15.30	0.46	11.76	8.32	3.43	143.70	91.25
AKLJ-11	18.60	0.38	14.68	8.65	6.03	148.30	89.72
AKLJ-12	13.20	0.47	10.33	6.72	3.61	151.40	91.30
AKLJ-13	16.30	0.42	10.46	7.61	2.85	140.30	84.35
AKLJ-14	19.37	0.26	14.67	10.06	4.61	160.20	95.57
AKLJ-15	18.90	0.46	12.44	8.64	3.80	157.40	93.20
AKLJ-16	16.10	0.41	10.32	7.73	2.59	153.20	94.12
AKLJ-17	12.80	0.50	8.48	5.91	2.56	147.20	89.62
AKLJ-18	19.30	0.27	12.41	8.50	3.91	151.60	89.37
AKLJ-19	16.30	0.42	11.30	8.41	2.89	149.20	90.27
AKLJ-20	18.40	0.33	11.76	7.60	4.15	146.20	85.75
AKLJ-21	17.20	0.40	12.21	8.99	3.22	144.70	91.02
AKLJ-22	19.10	0.28	13.37	9.98	3.38	142.10	94.15
Range	12.80-19.37	0.26-0.50	8.48-14.68	5.25-10.06	2.56-6.03	134.60-160.20	81.95-95.57
Mean	16.48	0.39	11.49	7.84	3.64	145.10	90.15
SE(m)±	0.19	0.005	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.12	0.14
C.D at 5%	0.55	0.015	0.08	0.13	0.15	0.35	0.40